

Panagia Vellas (Red Church)

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Entry tags: Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Greek, Language, Religious Place

Panagia Vellas, otherwise known as Red Church (Kokkini Ekklesia) is a late 13th-century church, near the village Vourgareli in the Pindos mountains (Tzoumerka). The church is located in the mountain pass that connects Porta Panagia in Pyli, Trikala, and Kato Panagia in Arta. The church was built in 1293/4 by protostrator Theodore Tzimiskes and his brother Ioannis Tzimiskes, along with their wives, Maria and Anna Tzimiskaina. The founders are also depicted in a donor's portrait in the narthex of the church. The Greek inscription also references the Epirote ruler Nikephoros I (r. 1267-96) and his wife, basilissa Anna as the rulers of the western fortresses, clearly demonstrating their alliance with the Epirote rulers. The exterior of the church is decorated with brickwork and stone tiles, common in churches of this period and in this region.

Date Range: 1293 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Vourgareli in Tzoumerka, Epiros

Region tags: Greece

A mountainous area in the Pindos mountains, named Vourgareli.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: B. Papadopoulou, *Η βυζαντινή Άρτα και τα μνημεία της κατά την περίοδο του Δεσποτάτου της Ηπείρου*, Athens 2002.
- Source 2: B. Papadopoulou, “Η Κόκκινη Εκκλησιά στο Βουλγαρέλι της Άρτας: Στοιχεία από τη νεότερη έρευνα,” *Ηπειροχρον* 42 (2008), 323-345.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: N/A

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1967

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavation undertaken by A. Orlandos

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
 - Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Other [specify]: cross in square with dome and narthex

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - I don't know

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
 - Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Other [specify]: Initially it was a monastic church

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Other [specify]: not entirely, parts during WWII (door)

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Human-caused accident
– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– Once

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Virgin

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: protostrator-military figure

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: N/A

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: In all likelihood, a few times per year. Definitely on August 15, when the Theotokos is celebrated in Orthodox Christianity.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– I don't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Inscription on the wall above the entry mentions the founders of the church and the authority of the region.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Panagia Vellas (Red Church), Papadopoulou, Barbara. *Η Βυζαντινή Άρτα Και Τα Μνημεία Της Κατά Την Περίοδο Του Δεσποτάτου Της Ηπείρου*. Athens: Ταμείο Αρχαιολογικών Πόρων και

Απαλιωτριώσεων,, 2002.

Reference: Panagia Vellas (Red Church), Papadopoulou, Barbara. "Η Κόκκινη Εκκλησιά Στο Βουλγαρέλι Της Άρτας: Στοιχεία Από Τη Νεότερη Έρευνα", 2008.